

Non-invasive methods of monitoring Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticle toxicity in human liver HepaRG cells using impedance biosensing and Coherent anti-Stokes Raman spectroscopic (CARS) microscopy

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ABSTRACT

Functionalized nanoparticles have been developed for use in nanomedicines for treating life threatening diseases including various cancers. To ensure safe use of these new nanoscale reagents, various assays for biocompatibility or cytotoxicity *in vitro* using cell lines often serve as preliminary assessments prior to *in vivo* animal testing. However, many of these assays were designed for soluble, colourless materials and may not be suitable for coloured, non-transparent nanoparticles. Moreover, cell lines are not always representative of mammalian organs *in vivo*. In this work, we use non-invasive impedance sensing methods with organotypic human liver HepaRG cells as a model to test the toxicity of PEG-Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles. We also use Coherent anti-Stokes Raman Spectroscopic (CARS) microscopy to monitor the formation of lipid droplets as a parameter to the adverse effect on the HepaRG cell model. The results were also compared with two commercial testing kits (PrestoBlue and ATP) for cytotoxicity. The results suggested that the HepaRG cell model can be a more realistic model than commercial cell lines while use of impedance monitoring of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles circumventing the uncertainties due to colour assays. These methods can play important roles for scientists driving towards the 3Rs principle – Replacement, Reduction and Refinement.

1. Introduction

Functionalized magnetic nanoparticles (e.g. superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles; SPIONs) have been widely used in research and various biomedical applications, including targeted drug delivery (Amiryaghoubi et al., 2023; Qiao et al., 2023; McBain et al., 2008), gene therapy (Li et al., 2023; Mu et al., 2018; El-Sherbiny et al., 2017), imaging and diagnosis (Anderson et al., 2019; Jeon et al., 2021; Kuhn et al., 2020) and hyperthermia therapies (Pucci et al., 2022; Gavilán et al., 2021; Bañobre-López et al., 2013). However, once these “nanoscaled machines” have finished their task, nanoparticle (NP) sequestration follows (Tsoi et al., 2016). In many clinical diagnostic and therapeutics, 99% of nanomaterials introduced into the blood stream are sequestered

and cleared by the liver (Tsoi et al., 2016), thus significantly reducing their numbers and capacity for effective target tissue efficacy. This sequestration mechanism generally starts with the adsorption of plasma proteins onto the NP surface to form protein corona (O'Brien et al., 2016). Various factors can influence the corona formation, including particle size, surface chemistry and charges (Diaz-Diestra, et al., 2022). These corona-tagged NPs are soon internalized by macrophages (phagocytes), preventing them from targeting the desired organs/tissues. Eventually, remaining nanoparticles are likely to accumulate in liver or spleen (Yin et al. 2018). In the liver, nanoparticles are taken up and cleared by a variety of cells, likely involving hepatobiliary elimination. Therefore testing nanoparticle compatibility, cellular uptake and sequestration shall use an organotypic *in vitro* human liver

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co-culture system of hepatocyte-biliary cells relevant to assess potential long-term effect in humans.

Conventional toxicity studies on magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) using rodents in cancer cell lines are widely reported, but given the importance of the liver in nanoparticle fate, it is perhaps surprising that very few studies utilize advanced human liver cell models. Moreover, most biological/toxicological assessments perform functional, although destructive, end-point assays. Therefore, the field would benefit from combining test systems which combining more organotypic human *in vitro* systems with non-invasive techniques to assess effects of NPs on human cells. Another issue for conventional toxicity assays is that they were designed for testing soluble substrates by measuring response via spectroscopy in the visible spectrum. Solid state nanoparticles, in particular black Fe₃O₄, can absorb visible radiation effectively, leading to possible errors on colorimetric assays particularly at higher concentrations, e.g., ≥ 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Hoskins et al., 2012). Moreover, the majority of studies on liver cell models with MNPs focused on developing contrast agents for MRI imaging (Wáng and Idée, 2017), whilst others address, for example, targeted drug delivery or hyperthermia to treat liver cancer (Surendran, et al., 2020). Few studies have been carried out on the interaction between MNPs and liver cells, possibly due to, in particular lack of physiologically-relevant human models. Among available liver cell models, human Huh7 cells are a widely used liver cell line which can reproduce some of the morphological, and biochemical features of human liver, and are used increasingly in studies on NPs and nanotherapeutics (Lunova et al., 2017). However, Huh7 and other 'standard' monoculture hepatocyte cell lines (e.g., HepG2; C3A) lack key metabolic functions of the fully differentiated adult hepatocyte phenotype, such as expression of specific CYP450s (Nelson et al., 2017). In principle, primary human hepatocyte (PHH)-based models should be ideal, but are limited in practice by scarcity of cells, high cost, short culture life-span, as well as phenotypic variability and instability in culture. To circumvent these issues, in this study, we utilize the human bipotential liver progenitor HepaRG cell line as a more appropriate organotypic model for testing biological effects of NPs. Following application of a well-validated differentiation protocol, HepaRG progenitors give rise to a uniquely stable, highly differentiated hepatocyte-cholangiocyte, co-culture system, in which liver-specific functions, such as expression of major CYP450s and drug efflux transporters and albumin and urea synthesis, are maintained for several weeks at levels comparable to those found in primary human hepatocytes (Jossé et al., 2008; Anthérieu et al., 2010; Parent et al., 2004).

In order to establish strategies for disrupting or circumventing the nanoparticle clearance mechanisms by hepatic cells to improve NP target delivery, a relevant, realistic liver cell model is required for evaluating the relationship between surface chemistry of nanoparticles and their parenchymal and non-parenchymal uptake profile. The magnetic property of magnetic nanoparticles used in this work permit also non-invasive tracking using MRI, without the need of fluorescent labelling which alters the surface chemistry of nanoparticles. Furthermore, the MNPs used in this work were PEGylated via silanization, which anchors short PEG polymers via strong covalent bonding, ensuring long term stability of MNP coatings. Non-invasive techniques were used to observe uptake and location of NPs in cells. Specifically, the effect of PEGylated and uncoated MNPs were continuously monitored using label-free/ non-invasive, impedance techniques, with two parallel colorimetric assays. Finally, Coherent anti-Stokes Raman spectroscopic (CARS) microscopy was used to study the effect of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles on HepaRG cells' lipid signature, which is an early indicator of cell injury. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) was used to assess sub-cellular MNP uptake in the human HepaRG liver cells.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Magnetite iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄) with an average diameter of 30 nm and cobalt (II,III) oxide (50 nm) were supplied by Alfa Aesar. 2-[Methoxy(poly-ethyleneoxy)_{9–12} propyl] trimethoxysilane (PEG_{9–12}-silane) was purchased from Fluorochem, U.K. Polyethylene glycol (BioUltra, Mw: 4000 g/mol and Mw: 400 g/mol), rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RITC) fluorescent dye and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were supplied from Sigma Aldrich, UK. Anhydrous sodium carbonate (reagent grade) and the solvents toluene (reagent grade) and methylated spirit (industrial 74 O.P.) were purchased from Fisher Scientific UK Ltd. Toluene was dried using activated molecular sieves (type 4 Å, general-purpose grade, Fisher Scientific UK Ltd.) in a closed container for 24 h. Phosphate buffered saline (Gibco™, PBS) was purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific UK Ltd. All chemicals were used as received without further purification. All water used was deionised water.

2.2. PEGylation of iron (II, III) oxide-MNPs via silanization

To chemically graft polyethylene oxide chains onto iron(II,III) oxide nanoparticles, 200 mg Fe₃O₄ MNPs were dispersed in 200 mL dry toluene (dried over activated 4 Å molecular sieves) using sonication. After 30 min, the suspension was degassed with N₂, and mechanically stirred at 300 rpm for 45 min. Then 1 mL of 2-[methoxy(poly-ethyleneoxy)_{9–12} propyl] trimethoxysilane was injected into the reaction mixture, which was then heated up to 110°C. The reaction mixture was kept under reflux with constant purging with N₂ gas and was stirred at 300 rpm for 4 h. The MNPs were then separated using a rare earth NdFeB magnet and washed with ethanol for at least 3 times to remove unreacted silane and toluene. After drying at room temperature overnight the particles were then dried at 80°C under vacuum for 4 h. The sample is denoted as PEG-Fe₃O₄ MNPs (Fig. 1a shows the PEGylation scheme using organosilanes). Prior to exposure to cells, all nanoparticle samples were sterilized using γ -radiation for 5 minutes using a shielded irradiator that contained around 120 TBq of caesium-137 and operated at 5 $\mu\text{Sv h}^{-1}$.

The PEG-Fe₃O₄ MNPs were characterized using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM). The chemical nature of the PEG coating was verified using a Nicolet is5 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific), fitted with an iD7 ATR-Diamond (KBr) attenuated total reflection sampling unit. A total of 16 scans per sample were recorded from 500 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . TGA for quantification of PEG coating was carried out using a TA Instrument STD Q600 thermobalance. In a typical experiment, a ca. 5 mg sample was heated in flowing air (100 mL min^{-1}) at a heating rate of 5°C min^{-1} to 800°C where the sample was held isothermal for 60 min. The normalised weight loss against a unfunctionalized MNP sample was used to quantify the amount of organic material (PEG) coated on surface. The particle morphology was studied using HRTEM. A FEI Tecnai TF20 microscope fitted with a field emission gun and operated at 200 keV was used for this purpose (in collaboration with the Kelvin Nanocharacterisation Centre, University of Glasgow). The samples were suspended in ethanol before being dispersed on holey carbon sample grids (Agar). The software ImageJ was used to measure the mean particle size.

2.3. Cell Culture

HepaRG cells (HPR116-TA08; Cryopreserved HepaRG cells; Biopredic Int., Rennes, France) were cultured using specialized media, following the supplier's protocols. Each medium was made up using William's E Medium with GlutaMAX™ (Sigma), as the basal medium; with appropriate additives (ADD). Additional methodologies are described in documents available online (Thermo-Fisher, 2023). Briefly,

Fig. 1. (a) Scheme illustrates the chemical grafting PEGylation on MNPs using PEG-silane. (b) Comparison on the FTIR spectra of unfunctionalized (i) and PEGylated MNP's (ii), showing characteristic bonds of the repeating unit in PEG coating. (c) HRTEM microgram of PEG-Fe₃O₄ MNPs and (d) particle size distribution of uncoated MNP (□), n = 321 and PEG-Fe₃O₄ MNPs (■), n = 423.

for each culture format indicated, HepaRG cells were seeded (day 0) at $2.4 \times 10^5/\text{cm}^2$ initially in Thaw, Seed and General Purpose HepaRG® medium (ADD670) on either 8-well ECIS microelectrode arrays (impedance measurements), Corning 96-well tissue culture plates (end-point hepatotoxicity assays) or Lab-Tek II chamber slides (immunocytochemistry). On day 3, medium was changed to HepaRGTM Maintenance and Metabolism Medium (MMM; ADD620), and HepaRGs cultured to confluence (terminally-differentiated hepatocyte:cholangiocyte co-culture); thereafter, medium was renewed every 2–3 days with MMM. Confluence on the electrodes is required prior to impedance toxicity assays, and for subsequent mathematical modelling, an algorithm embedded in ECIS used to deconvolve the multifrequency data (see Fig. 2; and Supplementary Fig. S1). On day 7, the cells were washed twice with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺) to prepare them for nanoparticle exposure. For each experiment/ assay - on day 7, cells were exposed overnight (24 hours) to 125, 250, 500 and 1000 µg/mL of non-functionalized Fe₃O₄ and PEG-Fe₃O₄ MNPs in serum-free media (the latter was used to minimize confounding protein-corona effects).

2.4. TEM imaging of HepaRG cells

HepaRG cells were exposed to Fe₃O₄ MNPs for 24 h and samples were then fixed in 3% glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M sodium cacodylate buffer, pH 7.3, for 2 h, followed by washing in three 10-minute washes of 0.1 M sodium cacodylate. Fixed cell samples were then post-fixed in 1% osmium tetroxide in 0.1 M sodium cacodylate for 45 minutes, followed by washing in another course of three 10-minute washes of 0.1 M

sodium cacodylate buffer. These samples were then dehydrated in 50%, 70%, 90% and 100% ethanol (3×) for 15 minutes each, followed by two 10-minute washes in propylene oxide. Samples were finally embedded in TAAB 812 resin. Sections of 1 µm thickness were cut on a Leica Ultracut ultramicrotome, stained with Toluidine Blue, and viewed in a light microscope to select suitable areas for investigation. Ultrathin sections of 60 nm thickness were cut from selected areas, then stained in uranyl acetate and lead citrate, and viewed in a JEOL JEM-1400 Plus TEM operated at 80 kV to analyze particle distribution and cell adsorption. Representative images were collected on a GATAN OneView camera.

2.5. Cytotoxicity colorimetric assays

Following exposure to the colloidal nanoparticle solution, the cells were washed 3× with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS with Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺) and cell viability was assessed using two independent cytotoxicity assays: PrestobluTM (Invitrogen) and an ATP depletion assay (Celltiter GloTM, Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. All viability data was normalised to the unexposed negative and lysed positive controls before statistical assessment via two-way ANOVA analysis. All experiments were triplicated and the standard deviation of the data were presented. Following cell viability assessment representative phase-contrast images were captured using an inverted fluorescent microscope (EVOS-FL, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Fig. 2. TEM images of HepaRG cells loaded with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles; unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs in (a) and (b) while PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs in (c) and (d). Dotted line boxes in (b) and (d) are magnified images of the areas of interest.

2.6. Monitoring HepaRG cells exposed to MNPs using non-invasive impedance technique

The cell viability was measured in real-time using the impedance based xCELLigence Real Time Cell Analysis (RCTA) instrument. HepaRG cells were seeded onto three 16 well plates at a density of 90,000 cells per well. The plates contained golden electrodes through which the electric current was measured continuously for 2 weeks. Once the cells were seeded the plates were connected to the xCELLigence system which was always kept in an incubator (37°C and under 5% CO_2 atmosphere). After culturing the cells for 7 days, with general purpose culture medium (GPS) the cells were fully differentiated and ready for nanoparticle exposure. On day 7, the cells were exposed to 125, 250, 500 and 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 and PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs in serum-free media. The impedance was measured for another 7 days, while keeping the plates in an incubator and changing media every two days.

2.7. Monitoring of MNPs with non-invasive CARS label-free imaging

Coherent anti-Stokes Raman spectroscopic (CARS) images were acquired using a custom built multi-modal multiphoton microscope (Mouras et al., 2011). This system consists of a mode-locked Nd:YVO₄ pump laser (PicoTrain, HighQ/ Spectra Physics) emitting 7 ps pulses at 1064 nm. Part of the output beam is frequency doubled to 532 nm which is used to synchronously pump an optical parametric oscillator (OPO) (Levante Emerald, APE) generating a tuneable output between 700 and 1000 nm. To match the $-\text{CH}_2-$ vibrational mode of lipids at 2850 cm^{-1} the OPO was tuned to 817 nm providing the pump beam and the 1064 nm output was used as Stokes beam. The two beams were coupled into an inverted microscope (Eclipse TE2000U, Nikon) with a modified Nikon 'C1' scan head. Both beams were overlapped spatially and

temporally on to the sample using a $25\times/1.05$ NA water-immersion objective lens (Olympus). All images were acquired with 125 mW (817 nm) and 85 mW (1064 nm) of excitation power at the sample plane (see Figure S1 in Supplementary Information). The forward directed CARS signal was collected using a 0.7 NA condenser lens (Nikon) and fibre coupled to a photomultiplier tube unit. The CARS signal was separated from the excitation beams using 700 nm and 785 nm short pass filters and a 660/13 nm band pass filter. Images were acquired with an exposure time of 64 μs and averaged 3 times over 5 regions per sample.

The number and size distribution of accumulated lipids were analysed using the Spot Detector plugin for ICY, an open access image analysis platform (Olivo-Marin, 2002). The image analysis protocol operates by first thresholding the images to detect cell colonies in the image field of view, the area of the detected region of interest (ROI) was then measured using the ROI statistics tool. The number of droplets within these defined ROIs were calculated using the undecimated wavelet transform detector, by detecting bright spots over a dark background. The results were manually checked for false positives and negatives and corrected accordingly. The number of lipid droplets per area of cell clusters was identified to compare between samples.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of PEGylated MNPs

PEGylated Fe_3O_4 MNPs were characterized using FTIR, TGA and TEM. Using FTIR, four characteristic adsorption bands of the polyethylene glycol (PEG) repeating unit at 1105, 1350, 1470 and 2870 cm^{-1} confirmed the identity of the PEG coating on PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNP surface (see Fig. 1b). A strong broad peak at 1105 cm^{-1} was

assigned to ether –C–O–C– band (1070 cm^{-1}) from the PEG chains as well as the silicon-oxide (Si–O) bonds of the silane. The other three peaks were assigned to the –CH– bending (1350 and 1470 cm^{-1}) and stretching (2869 cm^{-1}) modes of the polymer. TGA was carried out to study the organic composition of PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs. Comparing the thermogravimetric profiles of PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs with unfunctionalized MNPs, 3% weight loss was recorded when compared with unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs (see Figure S2 in Supplementary Information). From this result, it was estimated an average coverage of $66\text{ }\mu\text{mol}$ of PEG strands per gram of Fe_3O_4 MNPs, a comparable results to a prior study (Yiu et al., 2013) and an average footprint of each PEG strand at ca. 1.20 nm^2 on particle surface, consistent with published results (Yiu et al., 2013). HRTEM images of PEG-silane_(9–12) functionalized Fe_3O_4 (PEG- Fe_3O_4) MNPs were captured for studying the particle morphology, i.e. particle size and shape, and any change during silanization, as shown in Fig. 1c. The results showed that the PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs have a “pseudo-spherical” morphology with an average (mean) particle diameter of $29.9\text{ nm} \pm 9.8\text{ nm}$ ($n = 423$), with the majority of the nanoparticles between 20 and 35 nm in diameter (see Fig. 1d). Comparing with the particle size value of unfunctionalized MNPs, silanization did not seem to cause any significant change on particle morphology.

3.2. TEM imaging of cells exposed with Fe_3O_4 MNPs

Following exposure to Fe_3O_4 MNPs (i.e., both unfunctionalized and PEGylated), HepaRG cell were analyzed using TEM (Fig. 2), no major changes in overall cell morphology were observed. In both cases, the MNPs were considered to be internalized, likely via mechanisms such as phagocytosis or macropinocytosis, then accumulated in vesicles (Behzadi et al., 2017). However, clear intracellular differences were observed comparing unfunctionalized (Fig. 2a,b) and PEG- Fe_3O_4 (Fig. 2c,d) MNPs. Previous work has shown that unfunctionalized nanoparticles tend to agglomerate in a much shorter time than PEGylated samples (Suk et al., 2016; Patsula et al., 2019). Whilst both types of nanoparticle show deep cell penetration and distribution within the cell, unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles clearly mass with a much greater density than their polyethylene glycol coated counterpart (Fig. 2c,d), as highlighted in Fig. 2b. This observation is consistent with other PEGylated nanoparticles in cell media (Jenkins et al., 2016). This is important as it avoids large agglomeration in the circulation, which could induce thrombosis in blood vessels. Other functional surfaces such as carboxylate (Wills et al., 2017) and amine (Bagwe et al., 2006) also cause agglomeration, but they carry essential functionalities for drug or protein binding. For imaging purpose (e.g., MRI), a wider and more even distribution of nanoparticles to anatomical areas of interest would provide higher quality images.

3.3. Colorimetric methods for monitoring the effects of MNPs on liver cells

Colorimetric assays for monitoring the cytotoxicity effects of chemicals have been widely used since these convenient off-the-shelf kits can readily provide a ‘snap-shot’ *in vitro* cytotoxicity assessment of newly developed materials on selected cell lines. However, at present, precisely which assays are most appropriate for assessing nanotoxicity is unclear. In this study, two commonly used colorimetric cell viability assays: Presto Blue (non-invasive) and ATP-depletion assay (an end-point assay) were used to study the effect of MNPs on HepaRG cells (Fig. 3). Both assays demonstrated a comparable trend, indicating higher cell viability associated with PEG- Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs). Then a decline in viability was observed starting at a concentration of $250\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$. At higher concentrations (500 and $1000\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$), the difference between the two assays became obvious (based on the two-way ANOVA analysis). Generally, functionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs are considered to be non-cytotoxic at low concentrations, say $<150\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Olariu et al., 2011; Mahmoudi et al., 2012). This is correctly reported by both assays in this study. However, for MNP samples that may induce stronger cytotoxic effect, there is a possibility that the PrestoBlue assay may underestimate their toxicity, in contrast to the ATP assay, which might overestimate it. The origins of such a difference in reading can be difficult to pinpoint. Contradictory results on cytotoxicity from colorimetric assays on solid materials are not uncommon since most of these assays were designed for soluble materials (Hoskin et al., 2012; Willmann & Dringen, 2019). The problems associated with colorimetric assays for testing the cytotoxicity of coloured nanomaterials, including Fe_3O_4 MNPs, have been highlighted by several reviews (Mahmoudi et al., 2012; Willman & Dringen, 2019).

3.4. Cytotoxicity assay using non-invasive/ label-free impedance biosensing

Since, colorimetric assays can show inconsistent results for testing colour (nano)materials, there is a need to find alternative means to measure their cytotoxicity. Impedance based cell assays are increasingly recognised a highly sensitive non-invasive mean to measure in real-time phenotypic response to compounds (Gamal et al., 2017; Gamal et al., 2018). We used the xCELLigence unit for measuring the impedance over 14 days to analyse the HepaRG cell response to the nanoparticles under study (unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 , PEG- Fe_3O_4 and Co_3O_4) at three nanoparticles concentrations (250 , 500 , and $1000\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$) as shown in Fig. 4. A decrease in cell index indicates a decrease in cell number. Co_3O_4 nanoparticle was used as a comparison since cobalt (Chen & Lee, 2023) is considered to be a more toxic element than iron. Figures S3 in Supplementary Information showed the full impedance profiles for all experiments.

Fig. 3. Two common colorimetric assays for evaluating the cytotoxicity of MNPs, (a) PrestoBlue and (b) ATP, used to assess the cell viability upon exposure of nanoparticles. Key: light grey bar: unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs with cells; dark grey bar: PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs with cells. The error bars represent the standard deviation from three replicates. ($n=3$).

Fig. 4. Cell response reading from impedance measurements using the xCELLigence unit for 48 h period after HepaRG cells was exposed to unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 , PEG- Fe_3O_4 and unfunctionalized Co_3O_4 nanoparticles, at 3 concentrations: (a) 250, (b) 500 and (c) 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 48 h ($n=3$). Loading of nanoparticles is indicated with (★) while a change of serum-free medium (at the end of 24 h) is indicated by (▲). The control had no nanoparticle introduced.

From the results shown in Fig. 4, the most notable is that cell index from experiments with Co_3O_4 at all three concentrations showed a gradual decline against the control (no NP) since the introduction of NP samples (at around 160 h) over the monitoring period of 48 h. In general, for an impedance assay, the steeper the decline in cell index, the more toxic the material is. PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs showed slight decline in cell index again the control across all three concentrations but at much lower gradient than Co_3O_4 MNPs. Unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs showed

virtually no decline on cell index across all three concentrations, suggesting that PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs induced higher cytotoxic response than unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs. The results are not surprising as Co_3O_4 MNPs had been reported with toxicity on lung cells (Lugun et al., 2022), potentially due to reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated DNA damage. Although widely used, the PEG coating seems to have induced a degree of mild cytotoxicity when compared with unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs this is consistent with some literature (Webster et al., 2009). This is in contrast to the results shown from both colorimetric assays in Section 3.3. Indeed, there is also literature suggesting that the PEG coating may reduce cell stress through reactive oxygen species (ROS) as the cell does not recognise the nanoparticles as foreign bodies (Patsula et al., 2019).

3.5. Effect of MNPs on liver cells studied using CARS

Furthermore, a Coherent anti-Stokes Raman spectroscopic (CARS) imaging system configuration was also tested for monitoring the effects of Fe_3O_4 MNPs on cell behaviour parameters of HepaRG cells. In particular, we used CARS to measure the lipid signature spectra since lipid droplet (LD) formation is potentially an important hepatotoxic event. Indeed, LDs are implicated in a range of liver diseases, whilst LD size can influence insulin sensitivity and the extent of lipid peroxidation, as well as the rate of β -oxidation in cells.

Following the analysis of lipid droplet accumulation in live HepaRG cells (Fig. 5), both unfunctionalized and PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs showed some formation of LDs (white dots), similar to that shown from the control. Fig. 6a shows that unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs have little effect on HepaRG cells in terms of the number of LDs formed when compared with the control. PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs show an increase in LDs formation. While it is normal for the control cells to form small lipid droplets (300–800 nm diameter) for metabolic processes, it was noticeable that the size distribution of lipid droplets changed after the exposure to unfunctionalized and PEG-coated MNPs. Fig. 6b shows the size distribution of the LDs induced by both MNP samples in comparison with control within the focus area of $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$. The control induced the highest percentage of small droplets (65% $< 1 \mu\text{m}$) compared to the cells loaded with MNPs (57% and 51% for unfunctionalized and PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs). PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs showed the highest percentage of larger droplets while unfunctionalized Fe_3O_4 MNPs were in between PEG-coated sample and the control. This could be due to the MNPs preferentially stimulating macro-steatosis (large LD formation) through lipogenesis, esterification and altered free fatty acid metabolism, or expression of proteins involved in the retention of lipids (Przybytkowski et al., 2009). Indeed, molecular differences in micro- versus macro-steatosis have been observed in human fatty liver disease using MALDI imaging mass spectrometry, and LD dynamics/ morphometrics may be important factors in examining injury/ disease pathogenesis (Alamri et al., 2019). (Przybytkowski et al., 2009). It can also be seen that the lipids induced by PEG- Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were spread wider intracellularly than the unfunctionalized samples. This again, may not only confirm a stimulated cell metabolism but also that nanoparticles tend to penetrate deeper into the cell than unfunctionalized NPs. These results also mirror those from impedance assays presented earlier that PEG- Fe_3O_4 MNPs cause more adverse effects on HepaRG cell growth.

4. Discussion

In vitro cytotoxicity assays are carried out routinely to assess the toxicity of newly developed nanomaterials. However, there are reports in the literature that raise concerns regarding the applicability of commercial colorimetric methods to assess the cytotoxicity of solid nanomaterials, particularly dark metal oxide materials (Hoskins et al., 2012). The principles of these assays were usually designed to exploit some redox reactions occurring in live cells (e.g. resazurin salt reduction assay) or generation of specific molecules that can trigger change in

Fig. 5. CARS Images of (a) HepaRG cells control; (b) HepaRG cells loaded with Fe₃O₄ MNPs; (c) from HepaRG cells loaded with Fe₃O₄ MNPs. Images on the left column are enlarged images of the area of interest highlighting the lipid droplets found in cells.

colour of an assay molecule via a redox reaction (e.g. ATP assay). For testing soluble organic molecules such as some drugs, these assays are mostly adequate. On the other hand, for insoluble solid nanomaterials, there are several problems that could cause inaccuracy to most colorimetric assays, and such interference can be very complex. Firstly, solid materials absorb and/or scatter incident light as well as fluorescent emissions. This is particularly problematic with dark materials such as Fe₃O₄ and Co₃O₄. Then, regarding assays measuring emitted fluorescence from molecules generated during the reactions, Fe₃O₄ (Hao et al., 2017) and Co₃O₄ nanoparticles (Moradi et al., 2020) have shown concentration-related quenching (reduction in emission signals). This quenching process is also affected by the surface functionality of the nanoparticles (Hao et al., 2017). Such phenomenon will only cause further uncertainty for these colorimetric assays. Furthermore, signalling molecules generated can be adsorbed onto solid state materials, following the Langmuir adsorption model (Giri et al., 2016), and the amount of molecules adsorbed was highly influenced by the surface area and the surface chemistry of the solid. With a high surface area to volume ratio, Langmuir effect is more prominent in nanoparticles. Again, the surface functional groups, particularly charged groups such as amino

and carboxylic acid groups, also play a role in influencing adsorption of organic molecules on surfaces (Yiu et al., 2013). Finally, many transition metal oxides (e.g., Fe₃O₄ (Gao et al., 2017) and TiO₂ (Wang et al., 2017)) and metals (e.g., Au (Nishigaki et al., 2020) and Ag (Santhanalakshmi and Venkatesan, 2011)) have catalytic activities, including redox, and could interfere with the redox reactions involved in the assays (e.g., PrestoBlue – see vendor protocol). Metal and metal oxide nanoparticles will also further enhance this effect due to their elevated surface area. The extend of this interference is difficult to measure because of the complex environment including the (sometimes proprietary) composition of cell culture medium (Nelson et al., 2013). Finally, it is known that nanomaterials that bind to a cell can remain on its surface or return to the circulation or be internalized through receptor-mediated endocytosis, phagocytosis or pinocytosis (Tsoi et al., 2016). This further complicates the toxicity monitoring process. The combination of these factors makes colorimetric assays for solid state metal oxide NPs, such as Fe₃O₄ MNPs, inherently unreliable. As we have shown in this study using two different assays on the same NP samples, colorimetric methods can be inconsistent at high NP concentrations, e.g. ≥200 µg/mL, which is a relevant level for use of NPs in medical

Fig. 6. Analysis of lipid distribution in 2D HepaRG cultures after 24 h exposure with 50 μg of magnetic iron oxide (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles. The number of lipid droplets were detected per 100 μm² over 5 regions of interest on each sample (left panel) and the size distribution of droplets as a percentage of total (right panel). The numbers of droplets count (n) in each sample are: control, n = 247; unfunctionalized Fe₃O₄, n = 250; Fe₃O₄-PEG, n = 293.

research. Additional non-colorimetric assays could help to predict the cytotoxicity of newly developed materials.

In this study, we demonstrated that impedance assay can mitigate the uncertainty in absorbance for colorimetric assays due to coloured materials, as shown in Section 3.3. The design of the xCELLigence unit can carry out up to 6 × 96 well plates, a total of 576 experiments simultaneously in a high throughput fashion. In addition, real-time non-invasive measurements are another distinctive advantage offered by impedance assays over conventional colorimetric assays. Most of these commercial colour assays only allow measurements of one time point for one experiment. Vital information during the course of the experiment may get missed out. When HepaRG cells are used as test cells, impedance assays also allow longer-term continuous measurements, up to 7 days.

Standard treatments of cells for conventional histological (light microscopy) or confocal imaging techniques require destructive treatment of the sample (e.g., fixing, chemical-labelling). Despite being a gold standard for assessment of ultrastructural cell behaviour in cell biology/toxicology, including response to NPs (Tsoi et al., 2016), TEM is also an invasive, endpoint assay. CARS microscopy used here allows flexible label-free non-invasive monitoring of specific chemical bondings (chemical species) as well as molecules of interest, using fingerprints of the Raman spectra of cells (Moura et al., 2019). In this context, CARS is a particularly powerful tool for early diagnosis on some specific diseases. When compared with the colorimetric assays, including the two assays discussed in Section 3.3, CARS microscopy also offers a direct examination on the cells rather than relying on cell metabolic mechanisms. This can be significant as injured/damaged cells may still function and give positive signal for colorimetric assays.

The choice of using human liver HepaRG cells was carefully considered since the spent Fe₃O₄ MNPs are likely to be accumulated in the major parenchymal hepatic cells (hepatocytes:cholangiocytes). NP accumulation occurs also in liver non-parenchymal cells (e.g., Kupffer cells) as well as the spleen (Feng et al., 2018) and therefore any long-term damage is likely to occur in these two organs. Most *in vitro* liver studies on NP interaction with liver cells utilise 2D monocultures of human cell lines (e.g. HepG2/C3A) (Darwish et al., 2023) or rodent primary hepatocytes. HepaRG cells used in this study represent a realistic surrogate to phenotypically unstable primary human hepatocytes, as a reproducible and sustainable (>4 weeks) organotypic model for testing various functional components of NPs. Indeed, repeat-dose chronic studies may be particularly relevant to delineate potential long-term adverse effects of NPs. To further advance this HepaRG

model, an organotypic 3D human liver model, based on HepaRG cells can provide enhanced cell-cell/cell-matrix interactions, differentiate function and cell polarity, as well as markedly improve diffusion/transport conditions compared with 2D. Moreover, more realistic, human-relevant and ‘context-specific’ 3D models, incorporating hepatic non-parenchymal cells (e.g. endothelial cells; stellate cells; Kupffer cells) are likely to better reveal the potential for NP-mediated effects on liver cells, and potential mechanisms of action. In a 3D-human liver HepG2 spheroid model, toxic effects due to NPs (unlike parallel 2D cultures tested) correlated well with animal data (Tsoi et al.) by providing an *in vivo*-like microenvironment for more accurate assessment for NPs.

5. Conclusion

Since the liver is one the most important organs for blood purification, detoxification of chemicals, and metabolization of drugs, studying the effects of nanoparticles on liver is crucial to understand how hepatic cells behave after exposure to Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles. Even though colorimetric assays such as ATP (CellTiter-Glo) and PrestoBlue have been established as valuable cellular assays, some limitations, such as the absorption of light, can alter the data and produce inaccurate results and estimates. By analyzing liver function and cell behaviour in HepaRG cell cultures, an accurate estimation of the toxicity of nanoparticles can be made. The results presented here suggest that impedance-based measurements (xCELLigence system) and Coherent Anti-Stokes Raman Scattering (CARS) are powerful tools to analyse the cell viability of liver cells. Measuring the effects of nanoparticles on cultured cells label-free and non-invasively with the former provides a facile method to generate valuable nanosafety data - on both the immediate effects in real-time and for long-term exposures - whilst CARS can validate potential pathophysiological events, such as lipid droplets. Although 2D *in vitro* liver cell cultures are easily analysed in a 2D culture, where the cells have enough space to spread, they are not representative of *in vivo* liver cellular functionality, future work will focus on the development of 3D liver tissue models to mimic the liver’s behaviour more accurately. However, it should be noted there remain challenges to overcome for 3D liver model, in fact, due to their more complex cytoarchitecture and microenvironment, where cells form self-organized spheroidal aggregates; as these may pose a more difficult matrix to penetrate by nanoparticles. Additionally, further investigations into the cell response to free iron radicals are required to develop an understanding of the acute toxicity of ferrous nanoparticles at high

concentrations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Graham Anderson: Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Cyril Mongoin:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Guillemette Lafeuillade:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Humphrey Yiu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alison McDonald:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Joel Kuhn:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Alistair P.D. Elfick:** Methodology, Investigation. **Stephen Mitchell:** Methodology, Data curation. **Leonard J. Nelson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pierre O. Bagnaninchi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.02.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.02.010).

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Glossary

- PEG: Polyethylene glycol
 CARS: Coherent anti-Stokes Raman spectroscopic
 ATP: Adenosine triphosphate
 NP: Nanoparticles
 MNP: Magnetic nanoparticles
 MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging
 CYP450: Cytochrome P450
 PHH: Primary human hepatocyte
 TEM: Transmission electron microscopy
 PBS: Phosphate buffered saline
 FTIR: Fourier transform infrared
 HRTEM: High-resolution transmission electron microscopy
 ATR: Attenuated total reflectance
 TGA: Thermogravimetric analysis
 MMM: Maintenance and metabolism medium
 ECIS: Electric cell-substrate impedance sensing
 RCTA: Real time cell analysis
 OPO: Optical parametric oscillator
 NA: Numerical aperture
 ROI: Region of interest
 LD: Lipid droplets